

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. KRESTER M. DIAZ

Assistant Professor IV

Negros Oriental State University

kresterm Diaz@gmail.com

“PHONOLOGY AND LITERACY”

The importance of English Phonology from the perspectives of *Psycholinguistics* can never be underestimated in English language teaching and learning. It was in the era of 1950's to 1960's that phonology has made its biggest effect to the language teaching and learning both in second and foreign language learning.

As Scovel (1998) put it, one of the most influential ***psycholinguistic models for speech production***, developed by Levelt, views it as a linear progression of four successive stages: (1) conceptualization, (2) formulation, (3) articulation, and (4) self-monitoring.

At present, having a thorough knowledge of the basic speech sounds of a language or phonological system of a language is seen to be invaluable as it will benefit the learners greatly with improved language skills like reading and writing in particular. Stanovich (1993-94) in Sensenbaugh (1996) defines “phonological awareness” as the ability to deal explicitly and segmentally with sound units smaller than the syllable.

In an article on why phonological awareness is important for reading and spelling, Mots and Tolman (2009) stressed out that phonological awareness is critical for learning to read any alphabetic writing system. In fact, their research shows that difficulty with phoneme awareness and other phonological skills is a predictor of poor reading and spelling development.

To address the problem of students' reading and writing skills and its connection to phonology, Liberman and Shankweiler (1985) conducted a study on Phonology and the problems of learning to read and write. Findings indicate that the success of learners, whether they are children or adults, is related to the degree to which they are aware of the underlying phonological structure of words. They further proved that poor reader are often unable to segment words into their phonological constituents and may have other phonological deficiencies as well, and learners' difficulties in naming objects and in comprehending sentences, for example, may also stem from a basic problem in the phonological domain.

The Importance of Phonological/Phonemic Awareness in Learning to Read

On the knowledge of language at the level of individual phonemes, knowledge of these language units, and skill at consciously manipulating language at this level, Hoover (2002) made a critical analysis on phonemic awareness as critical in the development in the reading literacy. Findings reveal that positive correlations

between these two measures exist when, in general, students with better performance on one skill (phonemic awareness) also have better performance on the other skill (reading) and vice versa (That is, when students with poorer performance on one skill also have poorer performance on the skills).

Another study that has given needed insights is that of Ford's Foestering Literacy Development in English Language Learners. Ford (2005) explored the connection between phonological awareness and reading and found out that, for English language learners, performance on measures of phonological awareness in kindergarten has been shown to predict success in reading, even in the later elementary school years.

Moreover, Justin (2001) underscores the importance of phonological awareness as a powerful predictor of future success in reading. She cited several leading researchers like Wagner, Rashotte, Vellutina, and Shankweiler who have studied and proven phonological awareness to be important for skillful reading. She furthered by quoting O' Shaughnessy and Wanson (2001) who articulated that the primary cause of reading disability for a majority of children lies in phonological skills such as phoneme segmentation, verbal memory, and name retrieval.

What happens when phonemic awareness is missing or underdeveloped? Tankersley (2003) mentioned Aram and Hall (1989) and Brashir and Scavuzzo (1992) who prove that cognitive studies of reading have identified phonological processing as crucial to successful reading so it seems logical to suspect that poor readers may have phonological processing problems. "The effects of training phonological awareness and learning to read are mutually supportive, and that reading and phonemic awareness are mutually reinforcing. Phonemic awareness is necessary for reading, and reading, in turn, improves phonemic awareness still further," Shaywitz (2003).

Therefore, from the above discussions, there is really an increasing evidence that such phonological awareness among learners at all levels has beneficial effects on proficiency in reading words.

The Importance of Phonological/Phonemic Awareness in Learning to Write

A study conducted by Liberman and Shankweiler (1985) on writing certainly suggests that "metalinguistic awareness in the phonological domain has been found to be also highly predictive of spelling success" (Liberman, Rubin, Duques, & Carlisle, in press).

Since phonological awareness has been reported predictor of literacy development in early school grades, Weinrich and Fay (2007) conducted an investigation to 80 first-grade students who were enrolled in nine classrooms within two small community, public schools from a Widwestern state to find out if there was any significant relationship between phonological awareness and literacy predictors of spelling abilities for first-grade children. Findings indicated that reading level and the ability to identify individual letters corresponding to sounds in given positions in words (sound-to-letter tasks) were significant predictors of spelling ability among these first-grade participants. Phonemic awareness, particularly sound-to-letter recognition, for Treiman & Tincoff (1997) in Weinrich and Fay (2007), has been documented as a key component of learning to spell, as word spellings are often constructed from how the word sounds instead of rote memorization.

Connecting the dots, Carter, et.al. (2004) explored the relationship between phonological awareness and writing development in monolingual Spanish speaking children. Results reveal that writing levels and phonological awareness correlate significantly, and that the presence of writing significantly increases the number of correct responses.

According to the National Centre of Literacy and Numeracy for Adults (2012), in order to become good decoders and spellers, learners need to first develop some basic understandings about print and how it relates to spoken English. They added that learners must have developed phonological awareness and phonemic awareness to do so.

Therefore, it can be claimed that having a thorough understanding and knowledge of the units of oral language and individual sounds in spoken words can really improve learners' writing skills. The discussions presented above ascertained that the learners' ability to understand spoken language and complexities of speech is really an important early step in learning to read and write. It is, therefore, safe to say that phonology with the advent of developmental psycholinguistics that studies children's ability to learn a language plays a very significant role in the development of students' literacy.

References

- Carter, S. et.al. (2004). The Relationship between Phonological Awareness and Writing. Retrieved from www.benjamins.com
- Hoover, W. (2002). The Importance of Phonemic Awareness in Learning To Read. Retrieved from www.sedl.org
- Justin, N. (2001). The impact of Phonological Awareness on Reading Acquisition: Discrepancy Between Research and Practice. Retrieved from www.scholarworks.gvsu.edu
- Moats, L. & Tolman C. (2009). Language Essentials for Teachers of Reading and Spelling. Retrieved from www.readingrockets.org
- National Centre of Literacy and Numeracy for Adults. (2012). Retrieved from www.literacyandnumeracyforadults.com
- Scovel, T.(1998) Psycholinguistics.Oxford University Press
- Sensenbaugh, R. (1996). Phonemic Awareness: An Important Early Step in Learning to Read. Retrieved from www.ericdigests.org
- Shaywitz, S.et. al. (2003). Overcoming dyslexia: A new and complete science-based program for reading problems at any level. New York: Knopf.
- Tankersley, K. (2003). The Threads of Reading. Retrieved from www.ascd.org
- Weinrich, B. & Fay, E. (2007). Phonological Awareness/Literacy Predictors of Spelling Abilities for First-Grade Children. Retrieved from www.asha.org